

Didactic strategy supported by a website to improve reading comprehension through fables in fifth-grade students at Colegio Integrado Puerto Parra

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18644845

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Abstract

Keywords:
*incentivise,
reading
comprehension,
strategy, website*

Objective: In the present research, the main objective was to design a website as a pedagogical strategy to improve reading comprehension through fables in fifth-grade students at Colegio Integrado Puerto Parra. **Methodology:** This research was developed under a qualitative approach and participatory action type, with a diagnostic test applied through the Lecturómetro and a satisfaction interview. **Results:** Among the findings, a direct relationship was found between reading speed and textual comprehension, as reading faster presents fewer distractions, facilitating the interpretation process. Regarding participation, there was a great acceptance by the students, reflected in the increased participation when carrying out the proposed activities. **Conclusions:** Therefore, it was concluded that the website is a tool that motivates and sparks the students' interest in improving their reading process, thereby strengthening their interpretative competence.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, very noticeable problems have been found in students' reading comprehension, where the scores obtained by the student population are well below the standards of external tests. These low results that Colombia has obtained, both in national and international tests, highlight the need to initiate and promote investigative and pedagogical processes to achieve better learning outcomes for students. Therefore, it is important to generate strategies that motivate students to read and, at the same time, improve their reading comprehension skills, as these literacy processes are crucial for the proper academic and professional development of the student in their life.

The research proposal is framed as a strategy to address the issues present in fifth-grade students at Colegio Integrado Puerto Parra, who face various difficulties in their reading comprehension levels. These levels of reading comprehension are related to the degree of development a reader reaches when extracting the information contained in a text, which are: literal, inferential, and critical.

According to the results of the *Evaluar para Avanzar* tests by the Ministry of National Education (MEN, 2021), students are at a literal level in reading comprehension, placing below the national average in the competency of "Recovering literal information expressed in text fragments." Which indicates that the majority of students are at a literal level of reading comprehension, a type of comprehension that will lead to other levels and focuses on the ideas of information, but they have not managed to consolidate their learning at a more complex level of comprehension.

It is evident that students are being affected by multiple factors that hinder their proper development of reading comprehension, such as, for example, lack of support, disinterest in reading, or traditional teaching dynamics, among others. All of this causes students not to achieve the basic competencies in reading comprehension in the Saber tests. Possibly, part of the students' lack of motivation toward reading is a problem of the educators and the reading strategies they implement in the classroom, where the learning processes do not focus on the student and fail to motivate or encourage their interest in learning and reading, not to mention the lack of teacher training regarding the use of ICT tools in the classroom.

Nowadays, ICTs become allies of educational processes by offering a great opportunity to promote reading among students. Digital tools and resources consolidate a great opportunity for educational innovation that makes it possible to energize the learning processes, where the student can feel more motivated to learn. In this innovation, the teacher becomes one of the key figures responsible for presenting information to the student, mediating between the content and the students' learning, and carrying out creative and playful activities that stem from the students' issues or focus on active learning. However, the implementation of technology in the educational field must be united and subordinated to pedagogical provisions, where educational innovation through technology is supported by pedagogical purposes and not the other way around (Calderón, 2013).

This is why ICT has become a significant tool for teachers, as it allows for better learning in students, motivates them to learn, and at the same time, they find fun and entertainment while learning. Therefore, the use of ICT in education has a significant effect on students' learning and the consolidation of skills for academic and professional life, which will facilitate their integration into the community. Ultimately, expanding educational proposals beyond the classroom is one of the opportunities that the use of technology as a resource offers (Romero et al, 2010).

At Puerto Parra Integrated School, the issue of reading comprehension is concerning, as

fifth-grade students show deficiencies in their comprehension development. In the latest national tests, the results obtained have been low due to the students' apathy toward reading, which leads them to prefer answering at random or giving up on the complex cognitive process of comprehension, making it difficult to have a real understanding of their exact level. Proof of this is reflected in the previously mentioned "evaluar para avanzar" tests, as it is extremely important for students to develop their reading comprehension at more complex levels, where they do not remain solely in the literal realm.

For this reason, the general objective was to design a didactic strategy supported by a website to improve reading comprehension through fables for fifth-grade students at Colegio Integrado Puerto Parra. To achieve this, it was necessary to develop the following exercises: first, identify the reading comprehension difficulties in the fifth-grade students of the school; second, plan a didactic strategy on a website that incorporates fables as texts to improve reading comprehension in the students; third, implement the didactic strategy that incorporates fables as texts to improve reading comprehension in the students; fourth and finally, determine the level of impact of the didactic strategy on reading comprehension in the fifth-grade students of Colegio Integrado Puerto Parra.

Now, the research was based on empirical references at the international, national, and local levels, so that they could serve as a guide in the process. To begin with, the study conducted by Pérez (2022) is revisited, which aimed to determine to what extent narrative texts improve reading comprehension among fourth-grade students at the José Cardó Educational Institution. To this end, he conducted a quantitative research study with a quasi-experimental design where he administered a 20-item test with dichotomous options on two occasions, which was validated by experts in the field. Thus, upon concluding the study, a significant improvement in students' reading comprehension was evidenced in the literal, inferential, and critical dimensions, as a result of the implementation of the narrative texts program based on the reading of stories, fables, and legends.

Regarding the Colombian landscape, it is possible to affirm that problems in reading comprehension are also present. In recent years, Colombia has implemented various strategies supported by ICT to improve the situation faced by student populations in the area of literacy. This is well exemplified in the research conducted by Montoya and Benedetti (2021), where they found various difficulties in the reading comprehension of students at an institution in Medellín.

The research results showed that the use of ICT, with the design of the virtual course in Moodle, had positive effects where students' reading comprehension significantly improved. According to the authors, the proposal made it possible for students to feel more motivated and interested in learning, where the virtual course consolidated a dynamic educational environment in which they could express their doubts, opinions, or feelings regarding the texts and activities carried out. Therefore, they conclude that the proposal had a positive pedagogical impact by developing various skills in argumentation and reading comprehension among the students. Additionally, thanks to the technological elements, the students had participation and the development of their critical thinking (Montoya and Benedetti, 2021).

In the local context, it is worth mentioning the research conducted by García and Hoyos (2021) in their study titled "The Magic of Pombo's Tales to Facilitate Reading and Writing Processes in Transition Grade Children at the Liceo Pedagógico La Dicha del Saber in the city of Bucaramanga." In it, the authors aimed to design a didactic intervention proposal using as a basis playful-literary workshops guided by the tales of Rafael Pombo, all to promote access to knowledge, values, and creativity in children.

The research used a qualitative methodology with the action-research method, where special importance was given to generating a pedagogical strategy that placed great emphasis on the reading room and integrated puppet works, songs, games, and all playful pedagogical resources that captivate the child toward new learning.

The research results showed that the pedagogical strategy of the storytelling room had a positive impact on the students, given that this type of active methodologies fosters creativity, motivation, and imagination while developing their communicative skills. Therefore, the researchers emphasize that the use of children's stories, in this case by Rafael Pombo, not only grounds the pedagogical action in the creation of a playful, didactic, and literary space but also benefits students' learning in their comprehension and interpretative skills (García and Hoyos, 2021).

Regarding the theoretical frameworks transversal to this research, two are mentioned: reading comprehension and ICT in education. Thus, reading comprehension is a complex, dynamic, and interactive cognitive process, where the reader makes a series of relationships, comparisons, and combinations between the new information in the text, their prior knowledge, and the context of the reading (Niño, 2016). Hence, reading can be considered the discovery of new worlds and realities, not only because it involves knowing and understanding a series of thoughts, knowledge, ideas, or proposals new to the reader, but also because, in reality, it is an activity that implies the rediscovery of what is already known (Carrasco, 2013). In that sense, reading activity, and comprehension itself, are fundamental elements for human development, as they consolidate an indispensable element for cognitive development and the acquisition of knowledge.

Therefore, reading comprehension involves a series of levels aimed at the correct interpretation of the text's information. These levels are gradually developed during growth, depending mainly on the initial stages of reading learning, because it is there that not only reading is taught, but also a taste for it is created. To consolidate a true understanding of the text, the reader must interpret it on three levels: literal, inferential, and critical-evaluative (Mineduc, 2013).

First of all, the literal level refers to the ability to understand a text in what it explicitly says, that is, when a child remembers and understands the information presented in the text. The literal level is the most basic element for approaching and understanding a reading as it consolidates all the information that is specified clearly and in detail (Mendoza, 2018). Regarding the inferential level, the cognitive process at this level involves the reader's interpretation of the information that the text implicitly provides. Therefore, it is based on and supported by an adequate literal comprehension, but it is very different from it as it refers to what is implicit in the text and the connections that are not clearly explained (Mendoza, 2018). Finally, the critical level of reading comprehension refers to the evaluative judgment or opinion that a reader forms about a text. According to Catalá et al. (2007) cited by Mendoza (2018), the critical level involves an exercise of evaluation and the formation of the reader's own judgments based on the text and their prior knowledge, with subjective responses about the characters, the content of the text, and the literary images. Consequently, the critical level not only brings with it a deep understanding of the reading but also requires the reader to present a series of arguments that support their opinion regarding the text.

Another perspective is offered by Lastre et al. (2018), who use the same categories and describe them as follows. The level of literal comprehension corresponds to the reconstruction of what is narrated, although not mechanically; it includes the basic recognition of its structure and focuses on ideas or data clearly established in the text (Lastre et al., 2018). At the inferential level, the primary objective is the production of conclusions, and because it requires some effort, it is not commonly practiced by

average readers. It fosters interaction with different fields of knowledge and integrates new information with the environment (Lastre et al., 2018). Regarding the critical degree, it is usually considered as an idea, since the reader can make a judgment about the text and accept or reject it, but with arguments. Critical reading is evaluative, in such a way that it involves the reader's education, their judgment, and their knowledge of what they are reading (Lastre et al., 2018).

This is also constituted as a person's ability to understand both objectively and subjectively what an author or writer intended to communicate and convey in a text. As Jiménez (2014) rightly explains, reading comprehension is a cognitive process that is subordinate to reading competence, that is, comprehension is part of the human linguistic capacity that each individual has to understand, construct, and reconstruct meanings of the world around them, the ability to read the world in each of the sign systems of which it is composed.

To improve reading comprehension, it is very important to implement strategies or activities aimed at reducing the shortcomings that the reader presents in the process. Correa and Zambrano (2020) argue that to generate relevant strategies that improve reading comprehension, the following should be taken into account: micro-skills, techniques, and resources and materials. This implies that it is necessary to carry out processes that involve memory, anticipation, perception, and self-assessment, as well as techniques that involve teamwork, information transfer, language games, among others; all of which are interwoven with dynamic and interactive literary resources and reference materials. Likewise, Solé (1992) argues that it is important to approach the reading process in three stages: before, during, and after reading.

Each activity carried out in the three moments will be aimed at playing a specific role in the individual's reading process. First, pre-reading activities should be aimed at helping students approach the text's topic, guiding the activity toward recognizing vocabulary or key concepts for reading comprehension, and energizing the activity by encouraging the formulation of hypotheses and predictions. Secondly, the activity during reading should be guided toward a deep understanding of the text, where the teacher can direct the activity by asking questions, clarifying doubts, or using available resources, such as images, to stimulate the student's curiosity and motivation. Finally, the activity after reading should focus on the construction and reconstruction of meanings, where each of the important elements of the text read is analyzed in detail with the aim of centering the process on the construction of students' literal, inferential, and critical comprehension (Solé, 1998).

Since fables were used for the development of these competencies, it is necessary to conceptualize them. It comes from the Latin "fabula" and can be defined as a brief literary tale of fiction, in prose or verse, with a doctrinal intention often expressed in a moral ending, and in which humans, animals, and other inanimate or visible beings participate, with human characteristics such as speech or movement (Peralta and Córdoba, 2019). There is usually a narrator who describes the events (actions) surrounding various characters in an unspecified place and time because, due to their close relationship with folk tales, they do not take place in a specific time. The text revolves around conversations between animals, who generally tend to be the characters in these types of stories, although people such as rude, jealous, or selfish children, as well as objects or prototypical elements, are also found (Rodríguez, 2010).

Regarding the concept of "ICT in education," Law 1341 of 2009 defines ICT as "the set of resources, tools, equipment, software programs, applications, networks, and media that allow the compilation, processing, storage, and transmission of information such as voice, data, text, video, and images" (Art. 6). These tools have become relevant in today's society because they enable access to all kinds of information, as well as

effective and swift communication between any individual who needs it. Beyond their everyday use, technology with an educational focus ensures more didactic learning processes based on the construction of knowledge useful for life (Southern New Hampshire University [SNHU], 2021).

Likewise, they can be generally classified based on the networks, terminals, and services they offer (National Medical Library, 2013). First, networks refer to the means by which access to ICT is obtained (home and mobile phone network, internet network, television network); second, terminals are understood as the devices that enable such access (operating systems, browsers, computers, multimedia players); third, the ICT services offered to users (email, access to information, entertainment, educational platforms, banking or government, communities around a topic).

Regarding reading instruction, Marqués (2001, as cited in Sáez-López, 2013) points out broad and varied advantages: the integration of interactive resources such as multimedia, the promotion of initiative, continuous intellectual training, literacy in digital competencies, flexibility and interdisciplinarity, the acquisition of information search and management skills, the strengthening of expression and creativity, and the diversification of communication. Thanks to the contribution of ICT in education and considering that websites are part of these technologies, for the completion of this research that envisions the creation of a website, it is necessary to thoroughly understand its definition (Ricardo and Acuña, 2020).

Regarding pedagogical strategies, for Rovira Salvador (2018), it is reflected in the set of actions that the teacher carries out, in a planned manner, to achieve the proposed learning objectives. In summary, didactic strategies require the development, by the teacher, of a learning system whose main characteristics include an organized and formalized program aimed at achieving the established objectives. That is to say, in order to apply these daily academic procedures, it is necessary for the teacher to plan and schedule in advance. Therefore, they must select and refine the techniques they consider appropriate and efficient when achieving the teaching-learning processes (Toala et al., 2018).

According to Romero (2021), "a website is a site with information and data about a particular topic that can be accessed from an internet search engine and is published by a person or company" (para. 5). These sites hosted on the web are identified by a unique URL that also serves to access them and are composed of sections based on the subtopics the author wishes to address.

Web pages aim, among other reasons, to make a proposal or project visible, offer contact channels with the site creator, generate communities around the main topic, disseminate specific content according to the author's interests, etc. (Romero, 2021). With an educational intention, websites are an enriching tool that supports the teacher's practice in the classroom, as it allows them to organize and manage resources or pedagogical material. Precisely, in light of these differences, it is possible to categorize them into: tele-information, institutional, with didactic content, among others (Navarro Peña, 2018). In particular, the web pages of didactic materials known as tutorial websites, teaching websites, or didactic materials are didactic in nature because their content is specially constructed to be used in educational settings (Navarro Peña, 2018). Although there are a series of elements included in a web page and a succession of techniques to host them, the creation of a website is not limited to gathering images, texts, or sounds and inserting them into a web portal editor. It is necessary, first of all, to establish the objectives of the website, as they define the direction of the content, the scope of the site, and its depth, in addition to specifying user interaction and designing the graphical interface. To do this, we start with some questions: Who is the audience of the website? and what does the website offer? In this regard, it is important that

educational websites use useful and engaging didactic resources to promote user access to information and, from there, the construction of learning (Navarro Peña, 2018).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The research was conducted using a qualitative approach, as it seeks to investigate and understand the perceptions and meanings of the studied population, which includes issues in the educational field and, therefore, the strengthening of reading comprehension skills. Under a participatory action research (PAR) method, since for the proposed exercise, PAR is relevant, as the researcher is immersed within the study area and will be able to intervene in its development. According to Colmenares (2012), social actors become active researchers, participating in the identification of needs or potential problems to investigate, in the collection of information, in decision-making, and in the processes of reflection and action. Regarding the procedures, discussions are shared.

Regarding the participants, the present study included a mixed population of 20 fifth-grade students from Colegio Integrado Puerto Parra, with the participation of 10 boys and 10 girls, randomly selected from the two existing classes. The participants range in age from 9 to 13 years, energetic, responsible, collaborative, participative, and curious. Likewise, the 20 students were subject to coding ranging from CIPPQ01 to CIPPQ20. Additionally, the following inclusion criteria were considered: being a student enrolled in the fifth grade at Colegio Integrado Puerto Parra, expressing the desire to participate in the research through informed consent signed by parents or guardians, and having extra time available for the development of activities.

The instruments designed for data collection in this research were: the Glifing Reading Meter (Diagnostic Test), the observation sheet, and the semi-structured interview.

The study population (20 students) underwent a preliminary diagnosis using a resource called the "Lecturometer." This test consists of a series of steps, in which reading accuracy, speed, and comprehension are evaluated. Each participant had to read aloud so that the research teacher could record the accuracy data, then they answered a 10-question multiple-choice questionnaire that explores literal reading comprehension. This test is part of the development of the first objective outlined in the research, based on a prior review and validation of the judgment of three experts in the field. The "Lecturómetro" by Glifing is a free tool that allows students, together with teachers, to carry out a step-by-step process to determine: reading fluency, how many words they read per minute, the level of reading comprehension the student is at, and their attitude toward the exercise of reading. This tool generates a results format where each of the evaluated items is reflected, allowing for a measurement of the information collected through this test.

To address the implementation of the didactic strategy that incorporates fables as texts to improve reading comprehension in fifth-grade students at Colegio Integrado Puerto Parra, the instrument used was the observation sheet, as this type of tool allows the researcher to integrate with the study group and thus maintain a direct relationship with them. The behaviors that the researcher must observe are: attitude toward the proposed activity, enthusiasm for the reading process, understanding of the activity to be carried out, use of resources and learning materials, level of student performance in the lesson, and the time allocated to the sessions. For the analysis of the collected information, both the positive and negative aspects observed by the researcher during the implementation were taken into account.

The tool implemented to analyze the level of impact of the website was the semi-structured interview. Through a focus group, corresponding to half of the sample, that

is, 10 students; additional, comprehensive, and relevant information was sought regarding the resource used and the learning outcomes achieved in the reading comprehension process.

The procedure followed to meet the objectives was divided into four stages. The first moment was identification, the second moment was planning, the third moment was implementation, and the fourth moment was analysis.

The first stage of the research development was called identification, to determine the reading comprehension difficulties in fifth-grade students at Colegio Integrado Puerto Parra. (Lecturometer). Here, the diagnostic test was administered using the "Lecturómetro" resource, which is based on an online and free test that allows for the identification of the accuracy, speed, and reading comprehension of the student participants in this study. On the other hand, the relevance of this instrument was certified by experts, in order to subsequently apply and tabulate the information.

Moment II focused on planning a didactic strategy on a website that incorporated fables as text, with the aim of improving reading comprehension among fifth-grade students at Colegio Integrado Puerto Parra. The pedagogical proposal was developed with formative activities, where ICT tools were used as an innovative resource that promoted the development of interpretative skills focused on overcoming reading deficiencies in different texts.

The implementation process incorporated the didactic strategy of fables as texts that allowed for the improvement of reading comprehension through the website, leading to the joint development and execution with the students. At this stage, the information was collected through the observation sheet where the most relevant data from each exercise was recorded session by session.

In Moment IV, called analysis, the aim was to determine the level of impact of the didactic strategy on reading comprehension among fifth-grade students at Colegio Integrado Puerto Parra, through semi-structured interviews in a focus group composed of half of the sample students. During this phase, the aim was to compare the diagnostic test and the final test to see if the strategy through the website generated learning in the students that would improve their reading comprehension skills. The purpose was to determine the perceptions of fifth-grade students regarding the website "Fantabuleando," leading to the identification of whether it generated learning in the students that allowed them to improve their reading comprehension skills. At the end of the implementation of the didactic strategy, a satisfaction survey was conducted with 16 fifth-grade participants, designed in Google Forms, in order to gather information about their level of appreciation, perception, interests, and expectations after developing the "Fantabuleando" website, as well as aspects that could improve it.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results are presented below based on the previously described moments.

The diagnosis began with the identification of accuracy, which can be defined as the precision an individual has when reading. In other words, it refers to the correct identification of the words that can be found within a text. To measure accuracy, in this test each student read the passage aloud while the teacher took notes on the errors without interruption. The results are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1

Results of reading accuracy.

As can be seen in Figure 1, 7.1% of the students have a percentage of errors between 20% and 49% when reading, while 92.9% have few errors. Even so, despite the fact that the majority in this result made few errors when reading aloud, ideally, students should not make any errors when reading aloud, as none of the students scored 0%.

Now, for the diagnosis of reading speed, it is necessary to define it as the number of words that can be read in a given unit of time, usually expressed in minutes. In other words, this reading skill refers to an individual's ability to read a certain number of words per second or per minute (w.p.m.); it should be noted that reading speed does not affect text comprehension. In Figure 2, the categories of reading speed are shown, divided by the number of words per minute and the levels of education. Similarly, in Table 1, the classification categories for reading speed are shown, where a scoring scale with a percentile from 0 to 100 is used. Finally, Figure 3 shows the results obtained from the students through the Lecturometer.

Figure 2

Reading per minute

Category	2°	3°	4°	5°	6°	7°	8°
Very low	≤ 26	≤ 56	≤ 69	≤ 72	≤ 90	≤ 117	≤ 117
Low	27-40	57-63	70-84	73-90	91-102	118-130	118-130
Average	41-82	64-104	85-117	91-137	103-141	131-166	131-166
High	≥ 83	≥ 105	≥ 118	≥ 138	≥ 142	≥ 167	≥ 167

- Shaded areas represent categories below the minimum expected performance for the corresponding grade level.
- Non-shaded areas represent the expected performance categories for each grade level.
- The number of words per minute in red indicates the minimum threshold expected for the grade level.
-

Table 1

Categories classification reading speed results

Category Reading Per Minute	Category Meter	Reading Percentages of Correct Words Per Minute (WPM)
Very low	Very slow	From 0 a 19
Low	Slow	From 20 a 39
Medium	Correct	From 40 a 79
High	Fast	From 80 a 100

Figure 3

Reading speed results

According to the results obtained from the reading fluency diagnostic assessment, 64.3% of the students fall within the "Very Low" category, meaning they read fewer than 72 words per minute (WPM). Furthermore, 21.4% were classified within the "Low" fluency range, averaging between 73 and 90 WPM. Finally, the remaining 14.3% of students were placed in the "Average" (correct) category, with a range of 91 to 137 WPM. It is noteworthy that the "High" proficiency category, defined by a rate greater than or equal to 138 WPM (adjusted per table data), recorded a 0.0% achievement rate. These results demonstrate that the vast majority of students perform within the lowest reading fluency brackets, falling below the expected mean for the fifth-grade level.

Ultimately, reading comprehension can be defined as the aptitude or skill required to interpret a text, clearly grasping the development of the content and interpreting its central ideas (Niño, 2016). This assessment facilitated the classification of data into four distinct categories: No Comprehension, Poor Comprehension, Fair Comprehension, and Good Comprehension. The percentages for each category were determined according to a standardized scoring metric that yields percentage-based results, allowing for the identification of each proficiency level (see Figure 4)

The preceding image illustrates a result generated by the Lecturómetro assessment within the reading comprehension item. The scale represents a percentage from 0% to 100% based on the students' correct and incorrect responses. Utilizing the individual student results and the percentage-based scale, the following data are presented:

Figure 5

Reading Comprehension Results

The results obtained and interpreted in Figure 5 indicate that 9.1% of students were categorized as having No Comprehension, 18.2% demonstrated Poor Comprehension, 27.3% were classified as Fair Comprehension, and 45.5% achieved Good Comprehension; all of these correspond to a literal comprehension level. The primary objective of the Lecturómetro diagnostic assessment was to determine the reading comprehension level of fifth-grade students at the Colegio Integrado Puerto Parra, revealing that the students are positioned at a literal comprehension level.

In this regard, it is essential to highlight that the literal level of comprehension corresponds to the recognition and understanding of information explicitly provided by the text. That is, at the literal level, the reader understands and identifies the information presented but does not yet interpret it. According to Murcia et al. (2018), the literal level of reading comprehension involves basic cognitive processes where the reader observes, compares, classifies, and organizes information. These stages, or basic processes, reflect an individual's reading comprehension.

Based on this parameter, literal reading is a process in which students scan the text and extract exactly what the author states. Thus, the task is to grasp the text's representational structure, aiming to reproduce information presented clearly and directly. In this sense, it is necessary to recognize key phrases and words related to the topic, as this level does not yet delve into the implicit elements of the text, as stated by León and Vargas (2019).

Given the diagnostic results, it can be concluded that one aspect potentially related to comprehension levels is reading fluency. This component showed the greatest difficulties, as the vast majority of students were categorized as "Very Slow." Consequently, it is necessary to encourage fifth-grade students at Colegio Integrado Puerto Parra to explore the website as a didactic tool to help develop and strengthen their literal comprehension, enabling them to progress to the next level of reading comprehension: the inferential level.

Based on this diagnosis, a proposal was designed using an online design tool that allowed for the creation of a website and facilitated content management: WordPress. This platform is based on an open-source software model; it is a computer application that enables the publication, editing, and modification of content, as well as its maintenance from a centralized interface.

The website design took into account color theory for education, as the use of appropriate colors, along with their correct combination and placement, can significantly affect emotions, attention, and behavior during the learning process.

The site comprises a variety of fables presented not only in text format but also, considering inclusive populations, as audiobooks and videos designed for all types of users. It includes games for the comprehension phase and interactive workshops via Live Worksheets, which add interactivity and entertainment while allowing for the evaluation of participant progress. These games were designed using Word Wall, Educaplay, and PowerPoint, tools that facilitate the simple creation of interactive content. Evidence of their development is shown below.

Figure 6

Fable used on the website

Figure7

Fable proposed on the website

During the implementation of the didactic strategy, information was gathered through an observation sheet, where the most relevant data from the sessions were recorded. The recorded data evidenced that most participants demonstrated interest, dedication, concentration, and a committed effort to improve their comprehension skills.

Continuing with the analysis of the semi-structured interview, the data were divided into three categories to facilitate interpretation. The first category, "**Introduction**," aimed to identify the participants' preferences and opinions regarding reading. It was found that the vast majority of students receive support at home from their immediate family and dedicate between 15 and 30 minutes a day to reading. Regarding reading as a leisure activity, the interviewees' preferred genres are short stories; when asked what makes reading more engaging, many agreed that the use of images or illustrations is key.

The second category focused on the **students' perception of the website**. Participants described the platform using adjectives such as engaging, visually appealing, interesting, "cool," user-friendly, and fun, suggesting that it effectively captured their attention. Among other aspects mentioned by the students, the impact on improving their reading and comprehension competencies stands out. Some participants stated that the tool aided their concentration, as they had to read carefully to complete the activities in both the games and the workshops; consequently, they had to establish a reading pace or fluency that facilitated text comprehension.

The final category addressed the **interests and expectations** of the participants regarding the website. When asked how the daily application of these activities would improve their reading, they responded that it would enhance both their fluency and text comprehension; furthermore, some noted it would help correct their intonation when reading aloud. This presents a positive outlook based on the definition of reading provided by **Mineduc (2013)**, which proposes that reading involves more than deciphering letter combinations; it entails comprehending information, applying it in daily contexts, and enjoying the activity. For this reason, considering student interests is fundamental to fostering a reading habit.

CONCLUSIONS

Prior to implementing a strategy aimed at improving text interpretation, it is essential to conduct an accurate diagnostic assessment of the student's reading comprehension level; this allows for progress monitoring and introduces the student to the enriching world of reading. Furthermore, the didactic strategy achieved a high acceptance rate regarding the design, organization, applicability, and content of the website, indicating that the design was engaging for the students and successfully piqued their interest in reading.

On the other hand, the utilization of ICT (Information and Communication Technology) tools, in this case, a website, makes it possible to create more dynamic and enjoyable lessons focused on the reading comprehension process. By incorporating new technologies, these tools offer advantages such as autonomy, self-directed learning, and collaboration, providing sensory experiences that promote meaningful learning.

Consequently, the students participated actively in the development of ICT-based learning strategies, which allowed them to move beyond being mere passive recipients and become dynamic participants in the context in which they apply their knowledge (Clavijo Cruz et al., 2011). This learning process assisted each student in identifying their strengths and weaknesses in reading comprehension.

Although several challenges arose during the implementation of the research—such as

hardware failures, the lack of a dedicated computer lab for primary education, the initial nervousness of the participants, and the students' limited computer literacy—these setbacks contributed to the overall enrichment of the experience. Each obstacle was progressively overcome, generating new learning opportunities for both the students and the lead researcher.

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